

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Welcome to the second regular issue in 2015. Allow me to gratefully thank the members of our editorial board for their effort and support to cover also in this issue such high quality contributions. Please consider yourself and encourage your colleagues to submit high-quality articles to our journal. I want also to further extend our editorial board: if you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record, please do apply for a membership in our editorial board.

In this regular issues, we have 5 accepted papers from 7 countries from two continents. In a collaborative research between Poland and Czech Republic, Robert Bucki, Poland, Bronislav Chramcov and Petr Suchánek focus on the problem of minimizing economic costs of making orders in the automated manufacturing system by Heuristic Algorithms for Manufacturing and Replacement Strategies. The authors Selem Charfi, Houcine Ezzedine and Christophe Kolski from France suggest expanding the functionalities of existing evaluation tools by proposing a user interface evaluation framework which is based on three different evaluation techniques and has a modular architecture. In a collaborative research between Brazil and United Kingdom, Norton Trevisan Roman, Paul Piwek, Ariadne Maria Brito Rizzoni Carvalho and Alexandre Rossi Alvares propose a scheme for sentiment annotation which has been shown to be a reliable multi-dimensional annotation scheme for sentiment in behavior reports. The paper by Bojan Rupnik, Domen Mongus and Borut Žalik from Slovenia presents a new method for evaluating the point density of LiDAR datasets by computational geometry. The researchers Hassan Saneifar, Stephane Bonniol, Pascal Poncelet and Mathieu Roche from France introduce their approach called Exterlog to extract terminology from log files which exploits the most relevant terms of the domain based on a scoring function.

Enjoy reading!

Cordially,

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